

1 **Parasite protein pirates host cytoskeletal modulator during invasion**

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18 **Abstract**

19 Host cytoskeletal rearrangements are an essential yet poorly understood component of
20 *Cryptosporidium* invasion. Guérin *et al.* demonstrate actin rearrangements occur
21 immediately during adherence and capture a unique mechanism of invasion using live-
22 cell imaging. The authors identify a parasite-secreted effector ROP1 recruited by a host
23 protein LMO7 involved in pathogenesis.

25 With over 40 *Cryptosporidium* spp. and their inherent ability to infect a broad range of
26 vertebrates including humans, mammals, and wildlife, the footprint of infection is vast
27 [1]. The burden of *Cryptosporidium* infection is the highest in developing countries,
28 leading to over 200,000 deaths annually in children under the of age 2 in Africa and
29 South Asia [2, 3]. This factor is further complicated as no vaccine is available for
30 *Cryptosporidium* infection and nitazoxanide, the only approved drug, has low efficacy in
31 immunocompromised patients and is not approved for use in children under 1 year of
32 age [4]. Therefore, work to identify novel therapeutic targets to develop more effective
33 drugs against *Cryptosporidium* infection is much needed.

34

35 The entirety of the *Cryptosporidium* life cycle is completed in the intestinal epithelium of
36 humans. During invasion, an electron dense band with an underlying network of
37 filamentous actin (F-actin) forms at the host-parasite interface, separating the parasite
38 from the host cell cytoplasm [5]. However, the parasitic effector proteins involved in the
39 process of this F-actin rearrangement and their molecular targets have not been
40 identified. The invasion process of *Toxoplasma gondii* has been far more explored and
41 its rhoptry proteins have been linked to invasion of the host cell [6]. Basic Local
42 Alignment Search Tool (BLAST) searches using sequences from *T. gondii* identified 12
43 putative *Cryptosporidium* rhoptry homologs found in the protein content of sporozoites
44 with undefined target and function [7]. Guérin *et al.*'s recent study investigates the
45 interaction of a novel *Cryptosporidium*-secreted rhoptry effector with a host protein
46 during invasion [8].

47

48 Guérin *et al.* first developed a real-time live microscopy assay to study *C. parvum*
49 sporozoite morphology during invasion of host epithelial cells [8]. The authors found that
50 invasion happens rapidly (≤ 2 minutes) and that the apical end of the sporozoite is fixed
51 to the host cell while the basal end contorts. To gain insight into the morphology of the
52 sporozoite relative to completion of invasion, the authors labeled the plasma membrane
53 of the host cell and the cytoplasm of the sporozoite with fluorescent reporters and
54 demonstrate a novel parasite behavior in which the sporozoite undergoes a bent
55 conformation resulting in engulfment by the plasma membrane. This event is
56 subsequently followed by the parasite straightening and becoming encompassed by the
57 host plasma membrane. Using an F-actin labeled cell line, the authors showed once the
58 sporozoite contacts the host cell, rapid actin polymerization occurs at the apical end of
59 the sporozoite and continues to develop in structure but is limited to the sporozoite
60 apex. These findings reveal novel *Cryptosporidium* morphology during invasion while
61 concurrently defining the kinetics of parasite invasion.

62

63 The authors hypothesized the sporozoite morphology observed is due to the rhoptry,
64 which exists only apically, and its potential role in invasion. The authors performed two
65 separate analyses of transcriptomic datasets examining *C. parvum* genes during
66 various life cycle stages and identified a subset of 54 co-transcribed rhoptry protein
67 candidates. These potential *C. parvum* rhoptry proteins were further assessed for
68 localization in extracellular sporozoites and intracellular stages by immunofluorescence.
69 The authors reported six candidates that displayed localization to only the sporozoite
70 rhoptry bulb, thus suggesting these as potential rhoptry effectors (**Table 1**). The authors

71 then showed all six rhoptry candidates are secreted during invasion and localized to
72 diverse compartments in the host cell, implying rhoptry effectors target various host cell
73 processes and structures. Interestingly, ROP1 accumulated in the cytoplasm of the host
74 cell at the cell periphery where *C. parvum* invasion occurs.

75

76 In mice, using ROP1-HA labeled sporozoites, the authors showed localization of ROP1
77 to be restricted to the apical side of the epithelium. To explore if ROP1 localization is
78 associated with F-actin at the host-parasite interface, the authors generated F-actin
79 enriched or depleted cell fractions. They found ROP1 binds to a component of the
80 filamentous network and is F-actin non-specific. To identify the target of ROP1, the
81 authors employed a high-throughput yeast 2-hybrid screen of the N-terminus of ROP1.
82 The authors reported 149 positive clones associated with a host protein, LMO7. To
83 examine the function of ROP1 during invasion, the authors ablated parasite ROP1
84 expression. They reported, in the absence of ROP1 expression, host LMO7 was
85 present at the infection site *in vitro*. Using LMO7 KO mice, the authors showed ROP1
86 localization to the infection site is lost, suggesting LMO7 recruits ROP1. When
87 quantifying parasite burden, LMO7 KO mice were observed to have increased parasite
88 shedding. In contrast, ROP1 KO parasites display reduced infection *in vivo* when
89 compared to WT parasites. The authors concluded that host LMO7 acts to protect
90 against *Cryptosporidium* infection *in vivo*, however, *Cryptosporidium* has evolved to
91 hijack LMO7 via ROP1 to enhance parasite burden (**Figure 1**).

92

93 This study demonstrates unequivocally that *Cryptosporidium* sporozoite adherence and
94 invasion both involve host cell actin rearrangements. Furthermore, this study explores a
95 rhoptry protein secreted during invasion, ROP1, can enter the host cytoplasm while the
96 parasite remains extra-cytoplasmic. Finally, Guérin *et al.* discover an interaction
97 between a host protein, LMO7, involving recruitment of ROP1 and establish that LMO7
98 is protective against *Cryptosporidium* as KO of LMO7 increases parasite burden. The
99 discovery of novel rhoptry protein candidates is a much-needed step forward in
100 understanding the pathogenesis of *Cryptosporidium* invasion. A crucial next step is
101 further exploration of the remaining identified rhoptry protein function and their targets
102 during invasion as understanding these will provide insight on *Cryptosporidium*
103 pathogenesis. Interestingly, protein kinase C- α (PKC α), a host protein involved in
104 binding and stabilization of F-actin, has been linked to susceptibility of *Cryptosporidium*
105 infection in humans [9]. Further investigation into these identified rhoptry effectors and
106 host PKC α may yield new information on the mechanisms of parasite invasion. The
107 findings presented here are instrumental to the field in understanding the pathogenesis
108 of infection and action of a parasite secreted protein.

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116 **Declaration of Interests**

117 The authors declare no competing interests.

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119 **References**

- 120 1. Leitch, G.J. and He, Q. (2011) Cryptosporidiosis-an overview. *J Biomed Res.*
121 25(1):1–16.
- 122 2. Sow S.O. et al. (2016) The Burden of *Cryptosporidium* Diarrheal Disease among
123 Children < 24 Months of Age in Moderate/High Mortality Regions of SubSaharan Africa
124 and South Asia, Utilizing Data from the Global Enteric Multicenter Study (GEMS). *PLoS*
125 *Negl Trop Dis*;10(5).
- 126 3. Kotloff K.L. et al. (2013) Burden and aetiology of diarrhoeal disease in infants
127 and young children in developing countries (the Global Enteric Multicenter Study,
128 GEMS): a prospective, case-control study. *Lancet.* 382(9888):209–22.
- 129 4. Khalil I.A. et al. (2018) Morbidity, mortality, and long-term consequences
130 associated with diarrhoea from *Cryptosporidium* infection in children younger than 5
131 years: a meta-analysis study. *Lancet Glob Health.* 6(7):e758–68.
- 132 5. Elliott, D. A., & Clark, D. P. (2000). *Cryptosporidium parvum* induces host cell
133 actin accumulation at the host-parasite interface. *Infection and immunity.* 68(4), 2315–
134 2322.
- 135 6. Dubremetz J.F. et al. (1998) Apical organelles and host-cell invasion by
136 Apicomplexa. *Int J Parasitol.* 28(7):1007-13.
- 137 7. Sanderson, S.J. et al. (2008) Determining the protein repertoire
138 of *Cryptosporidium parvum* sporozoites. *Proteomics.* 8, 1398–1414.

- 139 8. Guérin A. et al. (2021) *Cryptosporidium* rhoptry effector protein ROP1 injected
140 during invasion targets the host cytoskeletal modulator LMO7. *Cell Host Microbe*.
141 S1931-3128(21)00303-6. doi: 10.1016/j.chom.2021.07.002.
- 142 9. Wojcik G.L. et al. (2020) Genome-Wide Association Study of Cryptosporidiosis in
143 Infants Implicates *PRKCA*. *mBio*. 11(1):e03343-19. doi: 10.1128/mBio.03343-19. PMID:
144 32019797; PMCID: PMC7002356.

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147 **Figure 1. ROP1 hijacks host LMO7 to facilitate parasite invasion.** First, Guérin *et al.*

148 performed analyses of transcriptomic datasets examining the *C. parvum* stage-specific

149 genes. From these analyses, the authors identified 54 co-transcribed rhoptry proteins

150 (ROPs) as candidates and six of these candidates displayed localization to the rhoptry

151 bulb. Of these, ROP1 (cgd3_1770) colocalized with host LMO7 at the site of infection

152 [8]. In mice challenged with ROP1-HA labeled *C. parvum* sporozoites, ROP1 and LMO7

153 were found to colocalize at the apical surface of the infected cells. Guérin *et al.* then

154 assessed the impact of loss of host LMO7 or parasite ROP1 on infection by challenging

155 LMO7 KO mice with WT parasites and challenged WT mice with ROP1 KO parasites.

156 LMO7 KO mice showed enhanced parasite shedding when compared to WT mice while

157 ROP1 KO parasites showed reduced parasite shedding when compared to control
158 strain. Figure created with BioRender.com.

159

160 **Table 1. ROPs targeting of compartments of host-parasite interface**

Gene identifier	Other identifier(s)	Localization
Cgd3_1770	ROP1	Parasitophorous vacuole, host cell periphery
Cgd3_1780	ROP2	Parasitophorous vacuole
Cgd3_1710	ROP3	Parasitophorous vacuole, host cell cytoplasm
Cgd3_1730	ROP4	Parasitophorous vacuole
Cdg1_950	ROP5	Ring structure, host-parasite interface
Cgd6_3630	ROP6	Ring structure, host-parasite interface

161 Prefix cgd: *C. parvum* predicted proteins; ROP: rhoptry bulb protein.

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